

MUSICAL SOUND AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract. This article is about musical sound and its characteristics, sound source, sound types.

Key words: sound, noisy sounds, circle, drum, drum, plate, spoons.

МУЗЫКАЛЬНЫЙ ЗВУК И ЕГО ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена музыкальному звуку и его характеристикам, источнику звука, видам звука.

Ключевые слова: звук, шумные звуки, круг, барабан, барабан, тарелка, ложки.

The content of art is life, the reality around us, the person himself and his inner world, thoughts, feelings. Unlike other types of human activity, art absorbs reality by creating artistic images. It creates the universe in a form that directly affects a person's emotions and consciousness. But an artist does not copy life, events, things.

He selects the most general, typical characteristics of an image, understands them all, changes the appearance of the image, and then embodies it in the form of a painting, poem, or piece of music. Of course, the work of any artist preserves the personal feelings of the author.

Because the objective material of the external world is reworked separately in the artist's mind and reborn as an original, unique creation. However, at the same time, each creative work is also considered a product of public consciousness.

After all, it is related to a certain social psychology, country, historical event. The social side of artistic creativity is manifested in the way that a person feels the connection with his contemporaries and the past of his people and humanity through artistic images. True art, while creating eternal artistic values, also realizes the continuous connection of generations. Thus, works of art are pictures of both life and creativity.

But different types of art are not able to depict different aspects of life at the same level. Each type of art is distinguished by its own content and principles. So, what is the art of music? What are its goals and tasks? Music is the art of tone (intonation), an artistic reflection of reality expressed in sounds. It reflects existence in its own way, enriches it, and helps to understand and change it. It is known that music plays an important role in the life of society.

Music is definitely a part of a person's lifestyle and social life, during work and leisure time, and it is a unique tool that helps a person achieve spiritual values. It is an effective tool of aesthetic education that shapes the spiritual world and moral goals of a person. Music itself, its creators, performers, listeners, music culture is an important area of society's culture.

The concept of "sound" includes a number of different phenomena. A flexible object can serve as a sound source. It is known that the vibration of the body causes wave-like vibrations in

the air. such vibrations are called sound waves. the movement of sound waves affecting the auditory organ passes through the auditory nerve to the brain and creates a sensation of sound.

The world we live in is full of different sounds. For example: humming, knocking, rustling, hissing and other similar sounds are all sounds of real reality.

These are called noisy sounds. the voice of the singing singer and the sounds emanating from the musical instruments - lute, flute, chan, violin, piano, oboe, trumpet and other musical instruments are called musical sounds. all sounds are distinguished by their high and low or long and short sounds, and at the same time their own variety. the difference between noisy and musical sounds is that each musical sound has a definite pitch. noisy sounds do not have this characteristic. The main means of music, that is, means of expression, are musical sounds.

But noisy sounds are also widely used in modern music. Musical sound, according to I. sposobin, has its own characteristics and is a part of the system of specific sounds developed during the development of musical culture over the centuries. the system of sounds serves to express musical ideas and embody artistic images. The character of each musical sound is determined by four main characteristics.

They are height, hardness, timbre and extension. the height of the sound depends on the speed of the vibrating object. the faster the vibration, the louder the sound, and vice versa. 1 For example: circle, drum, drum, plate, spoon sounds.

So, sounds are divided into high, medium and low sounds according to their pitch. Loud sounds can be described with words such as "elegant", "gentle", "elegant", "crystal". Our compatriot famous female opera singer Muyassar Razzokova and the world famous female opera singer from Italy Monserrat Caballe are the owners of high voice. The part of the soprano voice in choral works mainly includes high sounds. violin, flute, flute instruments also emit loud sounds. Low sounds are more often described by words such as "thick", "rougher", "deep", "ma yin". Munajat Yolchiyeva, a famous singer, has a low voice.

The world-famous Russian opera singer Fyodor Shalyapin also sang in the lowest male voice, that is, bass. Musical instruments such as trumpet, contrabass, bassoon have low sounds. Middle tones are typical for choir voices, alto and tenor, and for instruments, cello, clarinet, horn, rubob, dutor. The words "soft", "thick", "like a human voice" can be applied to them.

Tenor voice owners are the famous opera singer of our country Ismail Jalilov, the most famous "tenors" in the world are singers such as Placido Domingo, Jose Carreras, Luciano Pavarotti, Andrea Bachelli. the loudness of the sound comes from the vibration width (amplitude) of the object. the wider the vibration width, the louder the sound, and vice versa.

The degree of hardness (crackling force) is called dynamics. the duration of the sound depends on the continuation of the vibration of the body. Real time is measured in seconds, minutes, hours, etc. Time in music is measured by certain pitches (see Chapter II).

In music, each sound is organized to a certain extent with the sounds before and after it according to its length, enters into a relationship determined by time. Based on this, a well-organized time-dependent structure characteristic of music emerges. timbre of sound is called its color.

The fact is that any sound, especially musical sound, has a complex composition. the sound source (body) vibrates as a whole, creating the main vibration speed, i.e., a low-pitched sound that is best heard. this sound is called the fundamental tone.

Dynamics (Greek - *dinamicos*) - has power.

rather, at the same time equal to half, one-third, one-fourth, one-fifth, etc. of the total length of the body. parts also vibrate. The vibration speed of each part creates its own sound. the pitch of such secondary and tertiary sounds is two or three times higher than the primary sound. Because the shorter the length of the body, the higher its vibration speed and the higher the pitch of the generated sound.

These additional, component tones are called overtones¹ or harmonics (see Example 3). In the tone of the main tone, the relative ratio of overtones in terms of hardness, their presence or absence, emphasizes the individual quality of the sound, its dissimilarity from other sounds. For example: without seeing a bell, we can distinguish its ringing from the ringing of a rattle, or the tone of our mother's voice is "unique" among many voices.

These four qualities are definitely manifested in each sound, as well as in the combination of a series of sounds that express musical thoughts and images.

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